

Mapping GDPR Roles and Responsibilities to Scientific Data Sharing Networks

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Introduction:

A key aspect of European data protection law is ensuring all parties dealing with personal data have clearly assigned legal roles, and by extension, responsibilities. Key roles defined by the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) include controllers, joint controllers, and processors.¹ One of the purposes of assigning these explicit roles is to ensure there is no gap in responsibility to protect the fundamental rights of data subjects as data are exchanged between multiple actors.

Question: What GDPR roles apply where a health research project is conducted using data accessed from one or more data providers?

GDPR Roles

- **controller:** a party that “determines [both] the purposes and means of the processing, i.e. the why and how of the processing.” (EDPB 07/2020, p 3; Art 4 GDPR).
- **processor:** a party that processes personal data “on behalf of” a controller (GDPR Art 4), i.e., only for the controller’s purposes and according to the controller’s instructions. (EDPB, paras 78,79)
- **Joint controllership** arises where two or more entities jointly participate in determining both the purposes and means of processing. (EDPB 07/2020, p 3) This may be through a common decision, or through converging, complementary decisions determining the purposes and means of processing, where the processing is inseparable/inextricable. Mutual benefit may be indicative of controllership, but is not alone determinative. (EDPB 07/2020, para 60)
- **Third Party** is essentially any party who is not a controller or processor (GDPR, Art 4(10)).

Data sharing

Data sharing refers to the practice of making data from scientific projects or healthcare available to (other) researchers for scientific re-use. Data sharing encompasses both collaborations where investigators pool their data together as part of a joint analysis, as well as the non-discriminatory release of data to qualified members of the scientific community. Broadly defined, data sharing is technology neutral, encompassing both sharing by transmission of physical copies of data, as well as other forms of access (e.g., remote access to a secure computing environment). Healthcare professionals may also share data with each other in order to inform the diagnosis or care of a patient (our analysis will focus on data sharing for scientific purposes).

¹ The GDPR also mentions sub-processors, third parties and recipients, but these are less relevant to our discussion.

Box 1. Test to determine GDPR roles

To determine a controller, the relevant questions are²:

- Are you appointed as controller according to a legal act for the processing in question? (explicit legal competence), or
- Is the processing necessary in order to carry out a task for which you are responsible according to a legal act? (implicit legal competence), or
- As a matter of fact, do you determine?
 1. the purpose or purposes that the data will be processed for,
 2. which personal data that shall be *collected** and processed,
 3. which categories of individuals that the processed data will refer to,
 4. whether the processed data shall be disclosed and to whom, and
 5. *for how long the personal data will be stored.***

** includes the collection from other sources than the data subject directly*

*** applies only to legitimate storage for the respective purpose; where several controllers process the same data, data may still be stored longer for those purposes*

Additional qualifiers that may help the identification of a controller are:

- You obtain a benefit from, or have an interest in, the processing (other than the mere payment for services received from another controller)
- The processing activities can be considered as naturally attached to the role or activities of your entity (e.g. due to traditional roles or professional expertise) which entails responsibilities from a data protection point of view
- You have entrusted the processing of personal data to an external organisation to process the personal data on your behalf

For a processor:

- You process the personal data for another party's purposes and in accordance with its documented instructions - you do not have a purpose of your own for the processing.
- You do not pursue your own purpose in the processing other than your own business interest to provide services.

For joint controllership

- Do you and (an)other party(ies) involved jointly determine the purposes and (essential) means of the processing?
- Does more than one party have a decisive influence over whether and how the processing takes place – either by a common decision or by converging decisions that complement each other and are necessary for the processing because they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means?

² EDPB, Guidelines 07/2020, Version 1.0, Annex I

Table 1. Who is (Joint) Controller for a Research Project Reliant on the Sharing of Personal Data?

	Data Provider (e.g., hospital or research cohort owner)	Data User (e.g., researcher)
Conclusion	Data Provider generally a THIRD PARTY for the research project	Data User generally a CONTROLLER for the research project

GDPR/EDPB Legal Test for Controllers: Who Determines the Purposes and Means of Processing?

Purpose of processing	<p>Determines hypothesis/research question</p>	
Who benefits from the processing? (additional indicator of determining purpose)	<p>Scientific recognition through publication/dissemination of results.</p> <p>Ownership of any resulting Intellectual Property.</p> <p>Commercialization of results.</p>	
Types of personal data to be processed.	<p>Determines the types of data needed to answer the research question as part of defining the research methods.</p> <p>Determines where relevant data will be obtained (e.g., existing data from a data provider)</p>	
Categories of data subjects to undergo processing	<p>Determines data subject inclusion criteria as part of research methods.</p> <p>Determines where relevant data will be obtained (e.g., existing data from a data provider)</p>	

	<p>Ensures each category of data subject requested is justified for the research question (where data subject level search is possible).</p> <p><i>-->is not determining essential means, but instead simply ensures data minimization.</i></p>	
<p>Whether and to whom data are disclosed</p>	<p></p> <p>Identifies research partners and infrastructure/tool providers necessary to pursue his research question and to subsequently to include in access request (or separate access requests).</p> <p>Required by data provider to keep data confidential.</p>	
<p>Where Multiple Entities Determine Purpose and Means - Are they Joint Controllers?</p>		
<p>Summary: Data User generally Sole Controller for the Research Project.</p>		
<p>Joint Controller Test: Does Each Controller Jointly Involved Have Decisive Influence over a Common/Complementary Decision that is Necessary for the Processing to Occur?</p>		
<p>Data Provider: Determines the purposes and means by which personal data will be made generally available for scientific research based on common criteria of scientific utility, <i>independently</i> on any particular Data User.</p>		
<p>Data User: Determines the purposes and means of the research project <i>independently</i> of any particular Data Provider.</p>		

